

RESPONSIBILITY IN THE FIELD OF HEALTH PROTECTION FROM EXPOSURE TO AMBIENT TOBACCO SMOKE AND THE CONSEQUENCES OF TOBACCO CONSUMPTION

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Annotation:

Requirements for the allocation and equipping of special outdoor places for tobacco smoking, for the allocation and equipment of isolated premises for tobacco smoking are established by the federal executive authority responsible for the development of state policy and regulatory regulation in the field of construction, architecture, urban planning and housing and communal services, together with the federal executive authority, performing functions for the development and implementation of state policy and legal regulation in the field of healthcare, and they must ensure compliance with the hygienic standards established in accordance with the sanitary legislation of the Russian Federation for the content of substances in the atmospheric air released during the consumption of tobacco products.

Keywords: *entertainment performances, tobacco consumption, ventilation systems.*

Introduction

Government measures to influence the price level of tobacco products are carried out by setting minimum retail prices for such products. The minimum retail price of tobacco products is the price below which a unit of consumer packaging (pack) of tobacco products cannot be sold to consumers by retailers, public catering, service providers, as well as individual entrepreneurs.

It is not allowed to demonstrate tobacco products and the process of tobacco consumption in newly created and intended for adult audiovisual works, including television and video films, in theatrical and entertainment performances, in radio, television, video and newsreel programs, as well as public performance, broadcast, cable and any other use of these works, performances, programs in which tobacco products and the process of tobacco consumption are demonstrated, except in cases where such an action is an integral part of the artistic idea.

In addition, citizens are obliged not to carry out actions that entail violation of the rights of other citizens to a favorable living environment without ambient tobacco smoke and protection of their health from exposure to ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco consumption, and individual entrepreneurs and legal entities are obliged to monitor compliance with legislation in the field of protecting citizens' health from exposure to ambient tobacco smoke. smoke and the consequences of tobacco consumption in the territories and in the premises used for carrying out their activities, and also to ensure the rights of employees to a favorable living environment without ambient tobacco smoke and to protect their health from exposure to ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco consumption.

In order to prevent the effects of ambient tobacco smoke on human health, prohibits tobacco smoking: in the territories and premises intended for the provision of educational services, services by cultural institutions and institutions of youth affairs, services in the field of physical culture and sports; in the territories and premises intended for the provision of medical, rehabilitation and sanatorium services; in long-distance trains, on long-distance vessels, when providing passenger transportation services; on aircraft, on all types of public transport (public transport) of urban and suburban communications (including on ships when transporting passengers on intra-urban and suburban routes), in outdoor areas at a distance of less than fifteen meters from the entrances to the premises of railway stations, bus stations, airports, seaports, river ports, metro stations, as well as at metro stations, in the premises of railway stations, bus stations, airports, seaports, river ports, intended for the provision of passenger transportation services; in premises intended for the provision of housing services, hotel services, temporary accommodation and (or) temporary accommodation; in premises intended for the provision of household services, trade services, catering, market premises, in non-stationary retail facilities; in the premises of social services; in premises occupied by public authorities, local self-government bodies; at workplaces and in work areas organized indoors; in elevators and common areas of apartment buildings; on playgrounds and within the boundaries of territories occupied by beaches; on passenger platforms used exclusively for boarding trains, disembarking passengers from trains during their commuter transportation; at gas stations. In addition, grants the right to individual entrepreneurs and legal entities to establish a ban on tobacco smoking in the territories and premises used to carry out their activities, as well as, in compliance with labor legislation, to apply incentive measures aimed at stopping tobacco consumption by employees. Tobacco smoking is allowed on the basis of a decision of the owner of the property or another person authorized by the owner of the property.: in specially designated places in the open air or in isolated rooms that are equipped with ventilation systems and organized on ships on long-distance voyages, when providing passenger transportation services; in specially designated outdoor areas or in isolated common areas of apartment buildings that are equipped with ventilation systems.

The Law lists the basic principles of public control. Among them: the priority of the rights and legitimate interests of man and citizen; voluntary participation in the exercise of public control; independence of subjects of public control and their independence from state authorities, local governments, state and municipal organizations, other bodies and organizations exercising certain public powers in accordance with federal laws; publicity and openness of implementation public control and public discussion of its results; legality of the activities of subjects of public control; objectivity, impartiality and integrity of subjects of public control, reliability of the results of public control carried out by them; mandatory consideration by state authorities, local governments, state and municipal organizations, other bodies and organizations.

Moreover, this does not mean the sale of cigarettes, but rather the offer to try them in use together with older comrades. Tougher sanctions are expected if such involvement is carried out by the parents or legal representatives of a person under the age of 18. It should be noted that we should

also talk about educational activities. It is the responsibility of citizens to take care of the formation of a negative attitude towards tobacco consumption in children. Numerous public organizations, sports events and other actions should contribute to this; - not to carry out actions that entail violation of the rights of other citizens to a favorable living environment without ambient tobacco smoke and protection of their health from exposure to ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco consumption. Citizens are obliged to comply with all prohibitions established by the anti-smoking Law, in particular, not to smoke in prohibited places, thereby violating the right of other people to a favorable environment. Smoking is prohibited, as a rule, in contact places, places with large crowds of people. In such places, people cannot always turn away or close themselves from the harmful smell. Therefore, strict adherence to the prohibitions established by the anti-smoking Law will not violate the right of citizens to a favorable living environment without ambient tobacco smoke and protection of their health from exposure to ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco consumption. It seems that in order to further improve the anti-smoking legislation and the implementation of state policy in this area, it is necessary to search for effective tools designed to strengthen the practical component of the newly adopted law. Such may be systemic legislative changes aimed at strengthening administrative and criminal liability for offenses in the field of public health protection from exposure to ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco consumption.

The main directions of the state policy on protecting the health of citizens from exposure to ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco use in order to reduce the risk of developing diseases, disability and premature mortality due to tobacco use are:

- a) implementation of a set of measures to protect the health of citizens from the effects of ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco use, prevent the onset of tobacco use, limit its use, especially among minors, in order to reduce the risk of developing diseases, disability and premature mortality due to tobacco use;
- b) ensuring that citizens are informed about the risks of tobacco consumption and its harmful effects on human health, as well as about the harmful effects of tobacco smoke;
- c) ensuring the availability of preventive, diagnostic and therapeutic care, effective drug provision to all persons who consume tobacco and wish to get rid of this harmful habit by creating a state program for the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of tobacco dependence (nicotine addiction);
- d) strengthening the material and technical base of healthcare institutions to ensure the implementation of a set of measures to restore and strengthen the health of citizens, promote a healthy lifestyle;
- e) improving the hygienic regulation of tobacco products and methods for determining the compliance of the content of tar and nicotine, other harmful substances contained in tobacco products and released with tobacco smoke during their smoking, established by the legislation of the Pridnestrovian Moldavian Republic and (or) other regulatory legal acts of the Pridnestrovian Moldavian Republic with indicators, taking into account the requirements of international legislation;
- f) Ensuring that business entities comply with relevant standards, norms and rules during the production and sale of tobacco products.

The rights and obligations of citizens in the field of protecting the health of citizens from the effects of ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco consumption

1. In the field of protecting the health of citizens from the effects of ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco consumption, citizens have the right to:

- a) a favorable living environment without ambient tobacco smoke and health protection from exposure to ambient tobacco smoke and the effects of tobacco consumption;
 - b) obtaining, in accordance with the legislation of the Pridnestrovian Moldavian Republic, information from state authorities, individual entrepreneurs, and legal entities on measures aimed at preventing exposure to ambient tobacco smoke and reducing tobacco consumption;
 - c) implementation of public control over the implementation of measures aimed at preventing exposure to ambient tobacco smoke and reducing tobacco consumption;
 - d) submitting proposals to public authorities on ensuring the protection of citizens' health from the effects of ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco consumption;
 - e) medical care aimed at ending tobacco use and treating tobacco addiction.
2. In the field of protecting the health of citizens from the effects of ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco consumption, citizens are obliged to:
 - a) comply with the norms of legislation in the field of protecting the health of citizens from exposure to ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco consumption;
 - b) take care of the formation of a negative attitude towards tobacco consumption in children, as well as the inadmissibility of their involvement in the process of tobacco consumption;
 - c) not to carry out actions entailing violation of the rights of other citizens to a favorable living environment without ambient tobacco smoke and protection of their health from exposure to ambient tobacco smoke and the consequences of tobacco consumption.
 3. The requirements for the allocation and equipping of special outdoor places for tobacco smoking, for the allocation and equipment of isolated rooms for tobacco smoking are established by the executive bodies of state power authorized by the Government of the Pridnestrovian Moldavian Republic and must ensure compliance with the hygienic standards established in accordance with the sanitary legislation of the Pridnestrovian Moldavian Republic for the content in atmospheric air of substances released during the consumption of tobacco products.
 4. For persons in pre-trial detention facilities, other places of forced detention or serving sentences in correctional institutions, protection from the effects of ambient tobacco smoke is provided in accordance with the procedure established by the executive bodies of state power authorized by the Government of the Pridnestrovian Moldavian Republic.
 5. To designate territories, buildings and facilities where tobacco smoking is prohibited, a sign on the prohibition of smoking is accordingly placed, the requirements for which and the order of placement of which are established by the executive body of state power authorized by the Government of the Pridnestrovian Moldavian Republic.
 6. Local executive bodies of state power have the right to establish additional restrictions on tobacco smoking in certain public places and premises.

Retail sale of tobacco products is carried out in shops and pavilions. For the purposes of this article, a store means a building or part of it specially equipped, designed to sell goods and provide services to customers and provided with retail, utility, administrative and household premises, as well as premises for receiving, storing goods and preparing them for sale; a pavilion means a structure with a trading floor and designed for one a workplace or several workplaces.

Literatures:

1. Боль в спине: разработка алгоритмов диагностики и лечения на уровне первичной медико-санитарной помощи Республики Узбекистан Авторы: Халимова Дильрабо Джалиловна DOI: 10.37200 / IJPR / V24I6 / PR260396 Страницы: 4132-413
2. АНАЛИЗ РАЗРАБОТКИ ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИХ АЛГОРИТМОВ В СОЮЗЕ ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН Халимова Дильрабо Джалиловна JCR. 2020; 7 (5): 848-849
3. Халимова Дильрабо Джалиловна, «АЛГОРИТМЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛИ В СПИНЕ», JournalNX - Многопрофильный рецензируемый журнал, IUCRTTA-2020, ISSN: 2581-4230, стр. № 47-51
4. Халимова Дильрабо Джалиловна, «АЛГОРИТМЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛИ В СПИНЕ», JournalNX - Многопрофильный рецензируемый журнал, IUCRTTA-2020, ISSN: 2581-4230, стр. 47-51
5. Халимова Дильрабо Джалиловна «БОЛЬ В СПИНЕ: РАЗРАБОТКА АЛГОРИТМОВ ДИАГНОСТИКИ НА УРОВНЕ первичной медико-санитарной помощи в РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН» Биология и интегративная медицина, № 2 (42), 2020, стр. 44-52.
6. Халимова Дильрабо Джалиловна «БОЛЬ В СПИНЕ: МЕДИЦИНА И КЛИНИЧЕСКАЯ ПРАКТИКА, ОСНОВАННЫЕ НА ДАННЫХ», ACADEMICIA, международный междисциплинарный исследовательский журнал, импакт-фактор: SJIF 2020 ISSN: 2249-7137, стр. № 1086-1089.
7. Халимова Дильрабо Джалиловна, «АЛГОРИТМЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛИ В СПИНЕ», JournalNX - Многопрофильный рецензируемый журнал, IUCRTTA-2020, ISSN: 2581-4230, стр. № 47-51
8. Халимова Дильрабо Джалиловна «БОЛЬ В СПИНЕ: РАЗРАБОТКА АЛГОРИТМОВ ДИАГНОСТИКИ НА УРОВНЕ первичной медико-санитарной помощи в РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН» Биология и интегративная медицина, № 2 (42), 2020, стр. 44-52.
9. Халимова Дильрабо Джалиловна «БОЛЬ В СПИНЕ: МЕДИЦИНА И КЛИНИЧЕСКАЯ ПРАКТИКА, ОСНОВАННЫЕ НА ДАННЫХ», ACADEMICIA, международный междисциплинарный исследовательский журнал, импакт-фактор: SJIF 2020 ISSN: 2249-7137, стр. № 1086-1089.
10. Халимова Д.Д. БОЛИ В СПИНЕ У СПОРТСМЕНОВ ТЯЖЕЛОСТЕЙ УЗБЕКИСТАНА // Биология и интегративная медицина. - 2020. - №. 3 (43).
11. Джалиловна, К.Д. (2021). Боль в спине и пояснице после Covid-19. ЦЕНТРАЛЬНО-АЗИАТСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ МЕДИЦИНСКИХ И ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫХ НАУК , 2 (5), 329-334. <https://doi.org/10.47494/cajmnns..390>